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AWARENESS OF HYPERTENSION RISK FACTORS AMONG UNIVERSITY STAFF IN ILORIN, KWARA STATE

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is a major contributor to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in Nigeria. Awareness of its risk factors is a critical component of prevention, yet evidence among university staff remains limited. This study assessed awareness of hypertension risk factors among University Staff in Ilorin, Kwara State and examined implications for workplace

health promotion. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 384 academic and non-Academic staff of AL-Hikmah University in Ilorin, Kwara State who were selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected using validated structured questionnaire administered online via google form. Awareness of hypertension risk factors and complications was assessed using dichotomous items. Descriptive statistics summarized awareness levels, while chi-square analysis examined the association between awareness and self-reported hypertension at $p < 0.05$. Overall, awareness of hypertension risk factors was high. Excessive salt intake was identified as risk factor by 78.2% of respondents, while 80.2% recognized regular physical activity as protective. Awareness of hypertension-related complications such as stroke and heart disease were reported by 78.1%. Awareness of workplace-based blood pressure screening or health education programs was comparatively lower (63.5%). There was no statistically significant association between awareness of hypertension risk factors and self-reported hypertension status ($X^2 = 1.25$, $P = 0.535$). Despite high awareness of hypertension risk factors among university staff, Awareness alone did not translate into reduced hypertension prevalence. Workplace health Promotion strategies should move beyond information dissemination to address occupational Stressors enable healthier lifestyle practices.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension; Awareness; Risk factors; University staff; Workplace health promotion.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension remains a leading modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular diseases worldwide and accounts for substantial proportion of premature mortality. In Nigeria, the burden of Hypertension has increased steadily due to urbanization, dietary changes, physical inactivity, and psychosocial stress (WHO, 2021). The asymptomatic nature of hypertension in its early stages makes awareness of its risk factors critical for prevention and early control. University staff constitute a unique occupational group characterized by sedentary work patterns, high cognitive demands, and workplace stress. Although educational attainment among this group is relatively high, evidence suggests that knowledge does not necessarily translate into healthier behaviour (Adeloye & Basquill, 2022). Awareness of hypertension risk factors such as excessive salt intake, physical inactivity, obesity, alcohol consumption, smoking and stress is a prerequisite for prevention but may be insufficient without supportive environments. Universities

Offer strategies platforms for workplace health promotion due to their Structured workforce and Institutional influence. Akinlua J.T et al, (2021) however, reported that limited data exist on awareness of Hypertension risk factors among university employees in Nigeria.

This Study therefore assessed awareness of hypertension risk factors among university staff and explored implications for workplace health promotion programs that combine health education with regular screening and supportive environments have been shown to improve cardiovascular risk profiles among employees (WHO, 2020). However, limited data exist an awareness of hypertension risk factors among University Staff in Ilorin, Kwara State, and even fewer studies have examined the implications of such awareness for workplace health promotion (Proper KL, Van Oostrom SH, 2019).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

- **Study design and setting**

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among staff of Al- Hikmah University, Ilorin Kwara State, Nigeria.

- **Description of the Study Area**

Al-Hikmah University is a private university located in Ilorin. Established in 2005, it is known for its commitment to providing quality education grounded in Islamic values and principles.

- **Sample Size Determination**

The sample size was calculated using Fisher's formula:

To determine the sample size for the study, the formula used for the population greater than 10,000 was used:

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Where;

n = is the required sample size.

Z = is the z-value corresponding to the desired confidence level (1.96 for 95% confidence).

P = is the estimated proportion of the population with the characteristics of interest (0.5).

q = 1 - p.

d = is the desired level of precision or margin of error (commonly 0.05).

Given Values:

Z = 1.96 (for 95% confidence level).

P = 0.50%

q = 1 - p = 0.5

d = 0.05 (0.5% margin of error).

Calculation:

Substituting the value into the formula:

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.50 \times 0.5 / 0.05^2$$

$$= 384 \text{ respondents.}$$

Since the population of each university is greater than 10,000, there's is no need to apply the finite population correction factor. Therefore, the sample size required for the study, using fishers' formula, is 384.

- **Sampling Technique**

A stratified random sampling technique was employed for this study to ensure fair representation of all categories of staff within Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Kwara State. The Staff population of the university consists of two major groups academic (teaching) and non-academic (non-teaching) staff who differ in their job responsibilities, levels of exposure, and possibly health awareness. Stratification was therefore necessary to achieve balanced representation and minimize sampling bias.

- **Study population and sampling**

The study population comprised academic and non-academic Staff of the university. A sample size of 384 was calculated using fisher's formula. Stratified Random sampling was employed to ensure proportional representation of both staff categories.

- **Data Collection Instrument**

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire adapted from validated hypertension awareness instruments. The questionnaire assessed socio-demographic characteristics and awareness of hypertension risk factor and complications using a dichotomous scale (Yes/No).

- **Validity and Reliability**

Content validity was established through expert review by public health specialists. A pilot study conducted outside the study population yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82, indicating good internal consistency.

- **Data Analysis**

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Awareness variables were Summarized using frequencies and percentages. Chi-square tests examined associations between Awareness and self-reported hypertension status. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

- **Ethical Consideration**

Ethical approval was obtained from the Faculty of Health Sciences Ethical Review Committee of Al-Hikmah University (FHS-ERC). Participation was voluntary, Informed consent was obtained electronically and confidentiality was maintained.

RESULTS

A total of 384 respondents participated in the study.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of the Respondents

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
25-35years	82	21.2
45-55years	234	60.8
65 and above	68	18
Gender		
Male	205	53.6
Female	179	46.4
Marital Status		
Married	283	73.6
Single	60	15.6
Divorced	41	10.8
Occupational Designation		
Academic staff	213	55.4
Non-Academic staff	171	44.6

Salary Grade		
Level 3-5	69	18.0
Level 6-9	143	37.2
Level 11 and above	172	44.8
Numbers of children		
0-2 children	47	14.2
3-5 children	216	54.2
6 and above	121	31.6
Total	384	100.00

The majority of the respondent were male with 53.2%. Most of the respondents were from age range 45-55years (60.8%) and 73.6% were married. 55.4% of the respondents were academic staff while (44.8%) of the respondents were level 11 and above salary grade and 54.2% of the respondents have 3-5 numbers of children.

Table 2: Awareness of Hypertension and Risk Factors.

Variables	Yes (%)	No (%)	Row total	Df	X ²	P-value	Remarks
1. Are you aware that excessive salt intake increases hypertension risk?	300(78.2%)	84(21.8%)	384		0.78		
2. Are you aware that exercise helps reduces risk of having hypertension?	308 (80.2%)	76 (19.8%)	384		0.88		
3. Are you aware that hypertension can leads to stroke /heart diseases?	300 (78.1%)	84 (21.9%)	384				
4. Have you ever attended any health education or BP screening program?	244(63.5%)	140(36.5%)	384		5.92b		
5. Do you know where to seek medical help for hypertension?	264(68.8%)	120(31.2%)	384		1.56		
Total column	1,388	480	1,920	4	9.488	< 0.001	Reject Ho

Most respondents demonstrated high awareness of major hypertension risk factors. Excessive salts intake was identified as a risk factor by 78.2% of respondents, while 80.2% recognized the protective role of regular physical activity. Awareness of hypertension complications such as stroke and heart diseases were reported by 78.1% of respondents.

Table 3: Knowledge of hypertension prevention and management.

Variables	Yes (%)	No (%)	Row total	Df	X ²	P-value	Remarks
1. Do you know that maintaining a healthy weight prevents risk of having hypertension?	308 (80.2%)	76 (19.8%)	384		0.88		
2. Do you know that taking of anti-hypertensive drugs regularly improves the management of hypertension?	300 (78.1%)	84 (21.9%)	384		3.92		
3. Do you know that regular health check-up helps detecting hypertension early?	244 (63.5%)	140 (36.5%)	384		5.92		
4. Do you know that smoking of cigarette increases risk of hypertension?	264 (768.8%)	120 (31.2%)	384		1.56		
Total column (X ²)	1,492	444	1,920	4	1,452	< 0.05	Ho Rejected

As shown in Table 3, respondents demonstrated a generally high level of knowledge about hypertension prevention and management. A large proportion (80.2%) agreed that reducing salt intake can help lower blood pressure, while 79.2% believed that maintaining a healthy weight can prevent hypertension. Furthermore, 67.7% agreed that antihypertensive medications should be taken regularly even when one feels healthy, highlighting fair medication adherence knowledge. Likewise, 75% of respondents believed that regular health checks aid in early detection, and 79.1% agreed that avoiding smoking and limiting alcohol intake can reduce hypertension risk. These results suggest that staff members possess good knowledge of preventive measures and management practices for hypertension, although there remains room for improvement in drug adherence, education and regular check-up practices.

Table 4: Socio-demographic and lifestyle factors.

Variables	Yes (%)	No (%)	Row total	Df	X ²	P-value	Remarks
1. Do you know that consumption of salty/processed foods frequently increase the risk of hypertension?	224(58.3%)	160(41.7%)	384				
2. Do you engage in physical exercise \geq 3 times per week?	232(60.4%)	152(39.6%)	384				
3. Do you know that consumption of alcohol regularly increase hypertension risk?	124(31.8%)	260(68.2%)	384				
4. Do you experience stress at work most days?	236(61.5%)	148(38.5%)	384				
5. Do you currently smoke cigarettes/tobacco?	40(10.4%)	344(89.6%)					
Total column(X ²)	856	1,920	1,920	4	13.26	< 0.01	Ho Rejected

Table 4, summarizes the lifestyle behaviours of respondents. About 58.3% admitted to frequently consuming salty or processed foods, which increases their risk of hypertension. Regarding physical activity, 60.4% indicated that they exercise at least three times a week, showing moderate adherence to healthy lifestyle practices. Only 32.3% of respondents reported consuming alcohol regularly, while 61.5% disagreed, indicating relatively low alcohol consumption among staff. Similarly, 42.7% strongly disagreed with smoking, reflecting positive behaviour against tobacco use. On stress, 61.5% of staff reported experiencing work-related stress most days, a factor that could contribute to elevated blood pressure levels.

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrated a high level of awareness of hypertension risk factors among university staff in Nigeria, Awareness of excessive salt intake, physical inactivity, and hypertension-related complications were particularly high. These findings are consistent with reports from similar studies conducted among educated working populations in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African countries (Abubakar II, et al, 2018). Despite this high level of awareness, no statistically significant association was found between awareness of hypertension risk factors and self-

reported hypertension status. This suggests the existence of a knowledge-practice gap, a phenomenon widely reported in hypertension and other non-communicable diseases studies as opined by O'Donnell MJ, et al, (2020). Awareness alone may be insufficient to drive sustained lifestyle modification without supportive environmental and organizational structures. Occupational stress, sedentary work patterns, and limited opportunities for physical activity within university environments may contribute to persistent hypertension risk despite adequate knowledge (Schnall, et al, 2022). Work-related stress has been identified as an independent risk factor for hypertension and cardiovascular diseases (Steptoe & Kivimaki, 2018).

CONCLUSION

Al-hikmah University Staff in Ilorin Kwara State, demonstrated a high level of awareness of hypertension risk factors. However, this awareness did not translate into reduced prevalence of self-reported hypertension. This finding reinforces evidence that awareness alone is insufficient for effective hypertension prevention and control (Egan et al,2020). Workplace health promotion initiatives should therefore adopt multi-component strategies that address behavioural, occupational, and environmental determinants of hypertension.

- **Recommendations**

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- Implementation of routine workplace blood pressure screening programs.
- Introduction of stress management and physical activity initiatives within university settings.
- Promotion of healthy food options in staff cafeterias.
- Longitudinal studies should be conducted using objectively measured blood pressure.

- **Public Health Impact**

The findings reveal a clear knowledge-practice gap, emphasizing the need for workplace health promotion strategies that extend beyond health education to include routine screening, stress management, and supportive environments. Also, the University staff demonstrated high awareness of hypertension risk factors, though this awareness did not translate into lower self-reported hypertension prevalence.

- **Conflict of interest**

The author, zeenat titilayo, MOHAMMAD declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding The publication of this manuscripts.

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